

ISic3716

I.Sicily inscription 3716

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

clay

Object

tile

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

found near the 'temple of Concord'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 39398

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136046

0. [---]

1. [? μηδε]ις [παρὰ τὸν ὄρον ---]

2. [--- το]ῦ ναοῦ βαινέ [τω - - -]

3. [--- ὁ ληφθ]εῖς ἀδικείσητ [αι ἀζημίως]

4.

Edition: PHI336052

1. [— — — — — — — — — — — — — — —]

2. [— (?)μηδε]ις [παρὰ τὸν ὄρον(?) — —]

3. [— — — το]ῦ ναοῦ βαινέ [τω — — — —]

4. [— ὁ ληφθ]εῖς ἀδικείσητ [αι ἀζημίως(?)]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 136046

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Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 36 no.8 fig.85

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